

Hypothesis: Distribution of Primes and the Logarithmic Expression

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Introduction:

In the study of prime numbers, an intriguing hypothesis emerges when examining the distribution of primes based on the expression:

$$Expression : \left\lfloor \frac{(n-1) \cdot (-\ln \sqrt{e/\pi})}{\ln(n)} + 1 \right\rfloor$$

The aim is to explore how this expression partitions the natural numbers into groups, leading to a distinctive distribution of prime numbers.

Background:

Understanding the distribution of prime numbers has been a fundamental challenge in number theory. Prime numbers exhibit a seemingly random distribution, but certain patterns and structures emerge when analyzing their occurrence within specific mathematical expressions.

Hypothesis:

The hypothesis suggests that the integer part of the expression mentioned above produces groups of integers. Remarkably, as the range of N increases, the count of prime numbers within each group tends to average around 15.

Mathematical Expression:

$$Expression : \left\lfloor \frac{(n-1) \cdot (-\ln \sqrt{e/\pi})}{\ln(n)} + 1 \right\rfloor$$

Experimental Results:

1. For $N = 2$ to 100,000:
 - Total Number of Groups: 629
 - Average Number of Primes in Groups: 15.24960254372019
2. For $N = 2$ to 500,000:
 - Total Number of Groups: 2,561
 - Average Number of Primes in Groups: 15.072322639575972
3. For $N = 2$ to 1,000,000:
 - Total Number of Groups: 4,206
 - Average Number of Primes in Groups: 15.01803843997147
4. For $N = 2$ to 10,000,000:
 - Total Number of Groups: 26,199
 - Average Number of Primes in Groups: 15.00666752229506
5. For $N = 2$ to 100,000,000:
 - Total Number of Groups: 160,996
 - Average Number of Primes in Groups: 15.001042303132544

Conclusion:

The experimental results demonstrate a consistent trend: as the range of N increases, the average number of primes in each group tends to stabilize around 15. This intriguing pattern, despite the apparent randomness of prime numbers, suggests a unique and systematic distribution that warrants further exploration and analysis.

Future Research:

- Investigate the impact of varying the parameters in the expression on the distribution of primes.
- Explore theoretical explanations for the observed distribution and its connection to known number theory concepts.

- Analyze the behavior of the expression as the range of N approaches infinity.

References:

1. Riemann, B. (1859). "On the Number of Prime Numbers Less Than a Given Quantity."
2. Hardy, G. H., & Littlewood, J. E. (1923). "Some Problems of 'Partitio Numerorum'; III: On the Expression of a Number as a Sum of Primes."